

Investigations on the Adsorptive Property of Silica Gel. Part I. Chemical Activity of Residual Water in Activated Silica Gel.

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It is well known that silica gel contains some residual water which is very difficult to remove. This small quantity of strongly adsorbed water seems to have great chemical activity. In the course of an investigation (unpublished) on the reaction between hydrogen sulphide and sulphur dioxide, it was noticed that these two gases (which do not interact in the dry state) combined with great vigour at the surface of activated silica gel. The present paper gives an account of the experiments on the hydrolysis of carbon tetrachloride by the residual water in activated silica gel. The experiments indicate the great chemical activity of the adsorbed water. The investigation was the result of a violent explosion in the laboratory caused by the development of enormous pressure, in a closed glass vessel in which carbon tetrachloride had been kept in contact with silica gel at 150°.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The silica gel employed was a commercial product supplied by the Silica Gel Corporation. It was purified by treatment with concentrated nitric acid and activated in an electric furnace at a temperature of 353° in a stream of dry and pure air. The activated gel had a water content of 3.35% as determined by ignition to constant weight in a platinum crucible at blast lamp heat.

FIG. 1.

The carbon tetrachloride used was a C. P. product which was tested for impurities and purified by the usual methods employed in organic

chemistry. The apparatus consisted of a U-tube (Fig. 1) containing silica gel heated to a proper temperature by an electric furnace N. Nitrogen freed from carbon dioxide and oxygen by passing through an alkaline solution of sodium hydrosulphate and dried over phosphorus pentoxide was bubbled through a bubbler A, containing carbon tetrachloride and then passed over the heated gel. The products of reaction were absorbed in a known volume of standard barium hydroxide, kept in C, which was protected by D from atmospheric contamination.

A weighed amount of the gel was introduced into the U-tube B, through H and the open end sealed off. Stop-cocks S_1 and S_2 were closed, the apparatus attached to a Hyvac pump at the ground glass joint G. The system was evacuated for an hour and the carbon tetrachloride was poured into A, through a dropping funnel F. After allowing the gel to adsorb carbon tetrachloride for 20 minutes, the nitrogen was allowed to fill the apparatus. The apparatus was then disconnected from the pump and the bubbler system was attached to it at G. The U-tube was then gradually heated up to the required temperature. Nitrogen was saturated with carbon tetrachloride in A, and passed over the gel at a constant rate of one litre per hour, till the baryta freshly placed at C, remained clear, indicating that the evolution of carbon dioxide had ceased.

Preliminary experiments indicated that the barium hydroxide in C, was converted into the carbonate and the chloride by the products of reaction. The excess of baryta in C at the end of the experiment was estimated by titrating the solution with standard nitric acid (N/10) using phenolphthalein as an indicator and taking suitable precautions to prevent the loss of carbon dioxide. A known volume of the standard acid was then added, the solution boiled to expel carbon dioxide and the excess of the acid determined. The chloride formed could indirectly be calculated with these data, but was also directly estimated by Volhard's method. There was good agreement between chloride value obtained by the two methods.

The products of reaction were tested for free chlorine and none was found ; but the presence of carbonyl chloride in them was revealed by the following experiment. The nitrogen issuing at G, was passed through toluene saturated with ammonia, and the precipitate obtained was shaken with absolute alcohol and filtered. The alcoholic filtrate gave test for urea (*cf.* Allen, "Commercial Organic Analysis," Vol. VII, p. 293). It has to be pointed out that at a certain stage

the gel contained no water. This shows that the reaction at the gel surface is a hydrolytic process and not any thermal decomposition of carbon tetrachloride. The rate at which the hydrolysis took place is indicated by the following values obtained when 2.6 g. of the gel were heated at 300°.

TABLE I.

CO ₂ (m.mole)	2.21	3.11	4.50	4.82
Time (hr.)	2	4	18	37

The gel contained 5.02 millimoles of water.

Effect of temperature on the rate of reaction.—Silica gel saturated with carbon tetrachloride and kept for three months at the laboratory temperature gave no indication of any hydrolysis. The lowest temperature at which the hydrolysis was detected was 119°. At 120° the carbon dioxide evolved in one hour was 0.304 millimoles per g. of the gel. At 200° the value was 0.041 and at 300°, 0.37 millimoles per g.

Residual hydrogen chloride in the gel.—It was noticed that the hydrogen chloride produced during the reaction was not completely removed from the gel by a stream of nitrogen. For instance at the end of an experiment, the gel was found to have 9% of HCl by weight and only traces of this could be removed by passing a stream of nitrogen through S₃ for 6 hours at 300°. Details of the experiment are given below.

TABLE II.

Wt. of gel.	Temp. of gel.	Duration of expt.	HCl absorbed by baryta.
1	2	3	4
1.500 g.	200°	45 hr.	2.75 m.mol.
2.699	330	37	11.89
2.148	400	30	10.47
Residual HCl in the gel.	Residual HCl in the gel by wt.	Total HCl produced.	CO ₂ absorbed by baryta.
5	6	7	8
2.61 m.mol.	6.35%	5.36 m.mol.	[1.29 m.mol.
7.47	10.22	19.36	4.97
6.07	10.33	16.54	4.08
HCl : CO ₂ .	Initial water in the gel.	Residual water in the gel as calc. from CO ₂ .	Remarks.
9	10	11	12
4.15	2.79 m.mol.	1.50 m.mol.	Reaction incomplete.
4.92	5.02	0.05	Almost complete.
4.04	3.99	0.01	Complete.

DISCUSSION.

When carbon tetrachloride hydrolyses, two reactions are possible :

In the first reaction, the production of each mole of carbon dioxide consumes two moles of water, while only half this quantity is required for the second reaction. In the experiment described the carbon dioxide evolved, corresponds to the reaction and so it may be concluded that carbonyl chloride and hydrochloric acid gas are the products of hydrolysis.

Experiments on the adsorptive power of the gel containing residual hydrogen chloride are described in Part II. For comparative studies, instead of silica gel, glass beads were employed in the tube B and nitrogen, saturated with water and carbon tetrachloride vapours were passed over the beads for 3 hours at 100°, 200°, 400° and 500°. Only at 500° a slow production of carbon dioxide was noticed.

The results show that the residual water in the activated gel has remarkable chemical activity in as much as, it can bring about at 110°, the hydrolysis of a comparatively inert substance such as carbon tetrachloride, hydrolysis of which normally begins at 500°. It is possible that the molecules of the residual water in silica gel are so oriented that the hydrolysis of the chloride is favoured. Reference to Table II (column 2) shows that it is possible to remove all the water in activated silica gel, by a prolonged passage of carbon tetrachloride vapour at a suitable temperature.

SUMMARY.

1. Carbon tetrachloride vapour has been found to react with the residual water in activated silica gel. The reaction is perceptible at 110° and takes place at moderate velocity at 300°, forming carbonyl chloride and hydrochloric acid gas.

2. All the water in the activated gel can be removed through this reaction which gives a gel that retains hydrogen chloride very firmly.